

Bases for Ontology of Digital Twin of Maintenance Process. A Railway Application

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Abstract

Determining the exact relationships between each component that comprises a digital twin is necessary for its definition. This study is focused on fully maintenance activities within a specialized railway maintenance provider. Exploring ontologies reveals relationships that are required to be determined, connecting the entities with essential data sources to build the digital twin of workshop maintenance management process. Objectives include ensuring traceability of records and timely data interpretation. This facilitates defining optimization levels and automation in decision-making, predicting risk levels during each review. Results reveal that the digital twin definition process starts by determining relationships among subsets of elements or entities in the maintenance process in a determinate domain and with the specific semantic. The research's potential extends to all rolling stock elements, emphasizing the current focus on specific mandatory inspections.

1 Introduction and background

To build an accurate and useful digital twin, it is necessary to have a well-defined ontology. An ontology is a conceptual model that describes entities and their relationships within a specific domain (Bao et al., 2021). It provides a shared vocabulary and semantic structure that enables accurate and consistent representation and sharing of knowledge. The main contribution of this study is to lay the foundations of a model to integrate, represent and relate the entities and data of a railway equipment maintenance management process and, from there, the creation of digital twin. For this purpose, a 9-phase process is proposed that considers from the definition of the object, through the identification of domains and ontologies, to the agile testing of the same models in order to obtain a rapid improvement in each twin.

Recent findings reveal a rapid increase in publications on "Digital Twin Railway Ontology" in the last four years, comparisons indicate an early-stage development in railway exploration. The focus remains on engineering stages, linking BIM models to digital twins, rather than representing railway processes directly. Out of 362 SCOPUS studied results until 2022 for "Railways Ontologies", only three are related to the Railway, suggesting a wide opportunity for model development and scientific discourse on that topic. Railway field studies emphasize the unique heterogeneity and complexity in rolling stock and infrastructure data due to the industry's historical roots.

Complex studies, like that by (Li et al., 2022), highlight the use of ontology as a knowledge expression method in digital twin composition, integrating entities with key elements. Extracting concepts from (Kim et al., 2020), a standardized structure for defining entities and classification, based on relationships, forms the foundation for building a digital twin. Rescued concepts for constructing data models include Class Subclass, Entity, LOD, Domain, relationship, and connection point, crucial for digital twin development. (Crespo Márquez, 2022a) proposes a model dividing the process into systems, involving data extraction, transformation, and conversion, leading to various systems for effective digital maintenance management. The ontology modelling of the complex system is implemented with the six basic elements of Graph, Object, Point, Property, Role, and Relationship (Lu et al., 2019).

2 Conceptual model

The development of a successful digital twin requires a solid methodological foundation that integrates management and computer concepts. The fundamental task is to define entities and relationships (ontologies) in order to form the Digital Twin's data model, which raises the question of where to begin.

2.1 Bases for Digital Asset Definition:

Addressing this, a minimum steps to define a Digital Asset are showing in Figure 1, acting as a guide for managing projects involving the generation of digital twins. Even while these processes seem straightforward, there is frequently a lack of practical vision. In digitization projects, diverse perspectives contribute to data confusion (Nagorny et al., 2020) necessitating methodologies to bring order. The proposed steps, crucially applied in our research, align the efforts of various agents involved in twin creation (technologists, clients, academia, business, financial).

Figure 1. Minimum steps to define the Bases of a Digital Asset.

- **Step 1: Digital Object Definition**

In order to define a Digital Asset in accordance with the value-adding principle, a physical thing must exist digitally (UNE-ISO 55000, 2015). A clear business objective should be the first step in defining the purpose. Once the purpose has been established, the to be represented—physical assets, procedures, or services—must be determined.

- **Step 2: Define the Context of Digitalization (Framework Selection)**

The selection of a management framework is essential, with an emphasis on managing physical assets and associated processes to achieve corporate goals. Asset managers anticipate varied scenarios based on asset configuration, necessitating diverse management needs, including asset criticality determination (Crespo Márquez, 2022b).

- **Step 3: Relevant Entities**

Hierarchical attributes are used to identify single entities until an asset is defined (Malakuti et al., 2020).

- **Step 4: Identification of Domains**

In defining entities, it is important to specify where they belong or not. Contexts are identified as domains, ensuring the inclusion of properties from diverse sets and domains (Fujitsu et al., 2021).

- **Step 5: Class Identification**

Classification is essential in creating a digital twin, describing heterogeneous attributes through ontology modelling (Bao et al., 2021).

- **Step 6: Definition of Unitary Rules – Entities Relationship**

Unitary rules define the Digital Asset, determining relationships, including criticality for asset maintenance management (Crespo Márquez, 2023).

- **Step 7: Digital Twin Data Model**

The Digital Twin integrates data and information about each asset, evolving along the life cycle with two main data models: Engineering models and Data-driven models (Talkhestani et al., 2018).

- **Step 8: Development of MVP (Minimum Viable Product)**

To avoid stagnation, develop small prototypes to measure success or failure, minimizing risk and time (Robinson, 2001).

- **Step 9: Increase and Correct**

Recalibration is essential in the dynamic construction of digital twins, closing the Improve loop in the proposed DMM framework (Candón et al., 2019).

2.2 Use Case: Procedure for the design of the Digital Twin, Rolling Stock Maintenance & Depot. Mandatory Inspections

What should be done if paper is the starting point for creating a high-level digital twin? Can this industrial issue be met directly? The current use case's development aims to provide answers to these issues. As a first step, Table 1 shows the business objectives (to be achieved with the Digital Twin), the objects and the relationship with the RAMI 4.0¹ and IIRA² models in each of its layers.

Table 1. Object definitions elements.

Business objectives	Functions / Objects	Description	RAMI 4.0 Layers	IIRA Layers
Digitization of "Suitability for Service"	Asset control	Real time control of location, situation, status and certification of machines and components. Asset KPIs	Business	Business view point
	Workshop control	Real-time control of workshop processes and their resources	Business	Usage view point
	Client interface	Client access to fundamental data of the contracted service	Business	Usage view point
	Fitness for service control and traceability	Certificate control and traceability of regulated/mandatory maintenance tasks	Business	Usage view point
Maintenance optimization	Degradation prediction	Flange degradation prediction based on measured data and recorded machine operation data by GPS	Functional	Usage view point

¹ RAMI 4.0: Reference Architecture Model for Industry (Plattform Industrie 4.0 RAMI4.0, 2018)

² IIRA: Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (Shi-Wan Lin (Thingswise/Intel, 2022)

Business objectives	Functions Objects /	Description	RAMI 4.0 Layers	IIRA Layers
	Scheduling and planning optimization	Optimization of the scheduling of preventive tasks (dynamic preventive maintenance) Tasks and frequencies that can be modified.	Functional	Usage view point

For them they have selected 3 types of digitized elements and specifically the use case focuses on the following systems:

- **Physical asset: Rolling system / Axle wheel degradation.**
- **Process: Completion of the biannual review IS2**
- **Service: Control of "Fitness for Service"**

In this regard, once the model's design has been defined, it is necessary to characterize the data inputs and outputs generated as a result of the suggested reengineering process. This reengineering takes into account the technologies to be integrated and, particularly, the use of a maintenance information system as a basic support for the digitalization of maintenance processes (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schema of relationship of data, systems, technologies, and processes.

In digitalization, initiating with a Computerized Maintenance Management System (CMMS) is key. Choosing and integrating CMMS wisely, instead of building a platform from scratch, offers significant benefits. This streamlined approach avoids unnecessary elements, ensuring efficient model exploitation. When creating a new digital twin for different processes, entities can be easily redefined with specific attributes for diverse life cycle stages. For example, data needed in Design differs from Maintenance, Operations, or Financial Management. The atomized nature enables a customized digital asset representation through a dedicated ontology.

- **Data and Systems Requirements**

The definition of the system architecture necessary for data extraction, transformation, and processing is another crucial step in the production of digital twins. This ensures timely availability of structured data aligned with the process-specific ontology. The architecture encompasses layers such as Data Source, Provisioning, Storage, Processing, and Consumption (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Data & System Architecture.

- **Classification and Domains**

The stage preceding digital twin construction involves defining its classes and domains. Crucial attributes determining the digital asset and its context are established. Attributes can be single values or functions composed of others derived from a specific model. In our case, we delineate entities for mandatory inspection within the rolling system, encompassing assets, tools, and resources.

- **Entities ontology and data model of Digital Twins**

The integration of elements defined in Figure 1 results in a scheme facilitating the individualization and interrelation of various components: data, systems, processes, people, and technologies. This scheme paves the way for constructing the digital twin. This model (represented in Figure 4) is crafted in the latter part of our study as a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). It serves as the foundational structure for computing relationships, giving rise to the digital twin overview.

Figure 4. Ontology and data Model Schematic Overview.

2.3 Future Actions (MPV): Ontology developed on PROTEGÉ

The next steps aim to develop an ontology scheme in already exists software for ontology creation and management (Standford, 2023.) like a Protégé®. With a user-friendly graphical interface, Protégé allows intuitive ontology creation, editing, and visualization. Leveraging the OWL (Ontology Web Language), it is widely utilized

in ontology research. Protégé empowers users to define classes, properties, instances, and relationships within domains. It facilitates ontology import/export, seamlessly integrates with other tools, and incorporates reasoning engines. The ongoing research involves using Protégé or another similar tools to create a real ontology, forming a structured foundation for transforming assets into data for the digital twin model.

3 Conclusions

The study's primary contribution is establishing a management process to define a digital twin in a 4.0 industry associated standard, particularly in railway maintenance management context. Although industry opinions on this matter are not currently 100% defined, our process collects your best practices and presents them as a step-by-step encouraging research and possible advancement. The model argues for practical knowledge reflection in ontologies defining digital twins. Aligning with models proposed in RAMI4.0 and IIRA brings a broader context to the management level beyond IT (Information Technology) and OT (Operational Technology) environments. Connecting the digital and management worlds is crucial, avoiding digitization without a clear purpose. Systemic perspectives and hierarchical decision-making, considering criteria like criticality, are vital in digital twin creation. The study aims to kick-start discussions on standard management models in the railway context, fostering practical and applicable digital twins in the industry.

Acknowledgements

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PROGRAMME

	Day 1 29th May	Day 2 30th May	Day 3 31th May
Doctoral Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>• <i>Gala Dinner</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>
64th ESReDA Seminar	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>ESReDA BoD meeting</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Seminar Sessions</i>• <i>ESReDA GA meeting</i>• <i>Gala Dinner</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Seminar Sessions</i>

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 1. WEDNESDAY 29 May

Start	End	Agenda Item
8:30	9:00	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:00	10:00	Introduction to Digital Twinning Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
10:00	10:30	BREAK
10:30	11:45	Introduction to Inverse Problems and their Probabilistic Treatment 1 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
11:45	12:00	COFFEE BREAK
12:00	13:15	Introduction to Inverse Problems and their Probabilistic Treatment 2 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
13:15	14:30	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:30	15:45	Predictive/Proxi modeling, explainability of models 1 Prof. Anna Kucerova (CTU Prague)
15:45	16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00	17:15	Predictive/Proxi modeling, explainability of models 2 Prof. Andras Benczur (SZTAKI, Hungary)

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 2. Thursday 30 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
8:30	9:30	Predictive/proxi modeling, explainability of models 3 Prof. Andras Benczur (SZTAKI, Hungary)
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Digital Twin aiding more effective Digital Maintenance Diego López de Ipiña_DEUSTOTECH
10:15	11:15	Proxi modeling for stochastic systems 1 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK
11:30	13:00	Proxi modeling for stochastic systems 2 Dr. Noemi Friedman (SZTAKI, Hungary)
13:00	14:00	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:00	14:45	PLENARY TALK: Digital transformation in maintenance and asset management. Guidelines for organizations. Prof. Adolfo Crespo_UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
14:45	15:30	Bayesian model updating and filtering and computational techniques 1 Prof. Juan Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)
15:30	15:45	COFFEE BREAK
15:45	17:00	Bayesian model updating and filtering and computational techniques 2 Prof. Juan Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 3. Friday 31 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
8:30	9:30	BIM technologies and digital twinning 1 Ing. Francisco Carmona (QuantIA S.L., Spain)
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Identifying the Future Skills Requirements of the Digital Maintenance era Felix Bayon_SIDENOR
10:15	11:15	BIM technologies and digital twinning 2 Ing. Francisco Carmona (QuantIA S.L., Spain) & Prof. Manuel Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK
11:30	13:00	Educative examples of the whole framework, summary Dr. Noemi Friedman (SZTAKI, Hungary)
13:10	13:40	Wrapping Up: Key Takeaways and Roundtable Discussion
13:40	14:25	COCKTAIL LUNCH

64th ESReDA Seminar Agenda

DAY 1. WEDNESDAY 29 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
16:30	18:00	ESReDA Board of Director meeting

DAY 2. Thursday 30 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
9:00	9:30	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Digital Twin aiding more effective Digital Maintenance Diego López de Ipiña_DEUSTOTECH
10:15	11:15	AI for the application of maitenance techniques
10:15	10:30	Artificial Intelligence as a driver for Prescriptive Maintenance: Limitations Joaquín Ordieres_UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
10:30	10:45	AI-Powered Models: Catalysts for Digital Twin Advancements in Industry 4.0 Maria Megía_UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
10:45	11:00	A Review of Hybrid Prognostics Applications for Power & Energy Systems Joxe I. Aizpurua_MONDRAGON UNIBERTSITATEA
11:15	11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45	13:00	IoT and DT
11:45	12:00	An innovative IoT device designed to enhance teaching performance through the application of digital twin technology Diego Casado_DEUSTOTECH
12:00	12:15	Edge-Based AI for Online Health Monitoring of Critical Water Desalination Pumps: Aingura IIoT Applications in the Digital Twin Era David Cruz_AINGURA

12:15	12:30	Self-powered instrumentation systems for IoT and Maintenance Jorge Marcos Acevedo_ UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO
12:30	12:45	Recalibration of Digital Twins via Mobile Agents Sascha Peitzsch_ FRAUNHOFER SIRIOS
13:00	14:00	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:00	14:45	PLENARY TALK: PLENARY TALK: Digital transformation in maintenance and asset management. Guidelines for organizations. Adolfo Crespo_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
14:45	15:45	DT Modelling and Simulation techniques I
14:45	15:00	A Petri net-based Digital Twin development for managing wind turbine blade maintenance Wen Wu_ UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM
15:00	15:15	"Towards Precision in Railway Corrugation Estimation: Employing CNN-1D Networks and Fractal Dimensions" Massoud Haghbin_ UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
15:15	15:30	Basic architecture for digital twin implementation for power electronics application José López_ CEN SOLUTIONS, Juan Gómez_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
15:45	16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00	17:00	DT Modelling and Simulation techniques II
16:00	16:15	Simulation on reliability analysis of linear consecutive K-out-of-n systems for Weibull parameter estimation with incomplete failure data Daniel Gaspar_ TECNICO DE LISBOA
16:15	16:30	Smart factory maintenance: building a predictive model of pathogen transmission during the food fabrication process Sébastien Delmotte_ MAD-Enviroment
16:30	16:45	Digital Twin-Assisted Predictive Maintenance (DT-PdM) Framework for Complex Systems: Preliminary Research through a Pilot Study Huxiao Shi_ Politecnico di Torino
16:45	17:00	Bases for Ontology of Digital Twin of Maintenance Process. A Railway Application Mauricio Rodríguez_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
17:00	18:30	45th ESReDA General Assembly
20:30	-	Gala Dinner

64th ESReDA Seminar

DAY 3. Friday 31 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
9:00	9:30	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Identifying the Future Skills Requirements of the Digital Maintenance era Felix Bayon_SIDENOR
10:15	11:15	Lines of value for DT and DM development: human centered and servitization
10:15	10:30	Vulnerabilities in the human factor-digital technology relationship in the railway system Sever Paul_AGIFER
10:30	10:45	The consideration of the Human-Machine Interface in the Safety Management System of the process industry Romulado Marrazzo_VAL-RTEC
10:45	11:00	DFMAS Project: IoT and DT application for evolution of services with low level of digitalization Antonio Sánchez_UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
11:15	11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45	12:15	PLENARY TALK Service: the red pill. How to make industrial service a reality Ibon Iribarren_TIMEPACK
12:15	13:10	Digitalization for sustainability and management
12:15	12:30	Digital Twin technology in Civil Engineering: research vision from the ENHANCE and BUILDCHAIN European projects Manuel Chiachío_UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA

12:15	12:30	<p>Sustainable maintenance and digital twin technology: a test case for evaluating integration potentialities</p> <p>Maria Grazia Gnoni_ UNIVERSITY OF SALENTO</p>
12:30	12:45	<p>Impact of digitization on physical asset management</p> <p>Javier Serra_ENAGAS</p>
13:10	13:40	<p>Wrapping Up: Key Takeaways and Roundtable Discussion</p>
13:40	14:55	<p>COCKTAIL LUNCH</p>
-	-	<p>Free visit to the Guggenheim Museum Bilbao <i>(Limited number of invitations. To attend, registration will be open during the seminar until all available invitations are filled.)</i></p>

Location

Turin Room at Faculty of Engineering (2nd floor), Deusto.
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There will be indicative arrows to reach the Turin room once reached the entry of the Faculty of Engineering

